

TRENDS IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF THE GREEN ECONOMY IN THE REGIONS

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Abstract: This article describes greenhouse gas emissions into the atmosphere in the world and in Uzbekistan, the environmental situation and its consequences. The necessary proposals and recommendations on the further development of the green economy in the regions have also been developed.

Key words: greenhouse gases, atmosphere, climate change, global warming, environmental risk, green spaces.

Today, regulating greenhouse gas emissions into the atmosphere, investing in green energy systems, phasing out coal and fuel oil power plants, transitioning to alternative energy consumption, stimulating the full use of wind and solar energy sources, as well as the widespread use of "green" technologies, and increasing energy efficiency are urgent problems in the world.

The practice of green stickers and environmental labels has emerged in the eyes of consumers as indicators of environmental friendliness and sustainable development. Many industries are beginning to adopt these standards as a way to promote greening practices in a globalizing economy. These standards, also known as sustainability standards, are special rules that guarantee that purchased products do not harm the environment and the people who produce them. The number of these standards has recently increased, and now they can help build a new, more green economy.

In order to implement the tasks defined in the New Uzbekistan Development Strategy for 2022-2026, increase the effectiveness of measures being implemented to ensure "green" and inclusive economic growth within the framework of the Strategy for the Transition of the Republic of Uzbekistan to a "green" economy, further expand the use of renewable energy sources and resource conservation in all sectors of the economy:

A) Program for the transition to a "green" economy and ensuring "green" growth in the Republic of Uzbekistan until 2030, aimed at achieving the following strategic goals:

reduction of specific emissions of greenhouse gases per unit of gross domestic product by 35 percent from the 2010 level;

increasing the production capacity of renewable energy sources by 15 GW and bringing their share to more than 30 percent of the total volume of electricity production;

increasing energy efficiency in the industrial sector by at least 20 percent;

reduction of energy consumption per unit of gross domestic product by 30 percent, including through the expansion of the use of renewable energy sources;

significantly increase the efficiency of water use in all sectors of the economy, introduce water-saving irrigation technologies on an area of up to 1 million hectares;

expansion of green spaces in cities by more than 30 percent by planting 200 million seedlings per year and increasing the total number of seedlings by more than 1 billion;

Bringing the republic's forest fund reserves to more than 90 million cubic meters ;

The Ministry of Energy, together with the Ministry of Economic Development and Poverty Reduction and the Ministry of Finance, within three months, will develop a Plan of Practical Measures for saving fuel and energy resources in economic sectors for 2022-2026, aimed at achieving the Target Parameters.

The Ministry of Economic Development and Poverty Reduction has been established as the authorized body for coordinating activities to promote the "green" economy and implement the principles of "green" growth, and reduce greenhouse gas emissions in economic sectors.

The Ministry of Energy has been designated as the authorized body for the development of "green" energy, in particular, the widespread introduction of renewable energy sources and hydrogen energy, as well as increasing energy efficiency and reducing the energy intensity of manufactured products .

The "Strategy for the Transition of the Republic of Uzbekistan to a "Green" Economy for 2019-2030," approved by the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan on October 4, 2019, is an important program for ensuring sustainable development based on the "green economy" in our country. Among the important tasks of the transition to a "green economy" are increasing the energy efficiency of the economy and the rational use of natural resources. These target indicators will be achieved through the modernization of technologies and the development of financial mechanisms. In the process of implementing the strategy for the period up to 2030, specific greenhouse gas emissions per unit of gross domestic product will decrease by ten percent from the 2010 level, and up to one hundred percent of the population and economic sectors will be provided with modern, affordable, and reliable electricity. The production and use of environmentally friendly motor fuel and automobiles will be expanded, and electric transport will be developed .

In society, ideas about the need to preserve natural resources for recreational and research purposes gradually led to the formation of scientific concepts based on ecological responsibility to future generations. The implementation of these ideas in practice should be solved by ensuring sustainable development. Sustainable development is understood as development aimed at fully satisfying the needs of the population and not jeopardizing the possibilities of meeting the needs of future generations. Sustainable development can be represented as a process that develops due to a synergistic effect based on the interdependent development of the "social"- "economic"- "ecological" triad. The economic approach to ensuring sustainable development implies the rational use of limited resources. The social approach will be aimed at ensuring social stability and cultural diversity on a global scale. The ecological approach should serve to ensure the normal functioning of any ecological system. The economic approach to the concept of sustainable development was founded by E.R. Lindal and J.R. Hicks. According to Hicks-Lindall's theory of the maximum flow of gross income, income must be generated while retaining gross capital. This involves the rational use of limited resources and ecological (natural resource, energy, and material-saving) technologies, the creation of ecological products, and waste management. The main problem in solving this issue is the problem of which capital (physical, natural, or human capital) will be preserved and how interchangeable different types of capital will be, as well as the problem of assessing

the value of these assets (environmental resources). As a result, the following two types of economic stability emerged: - weak - economic stability of natural and accumulated capital that does not decrease over time; - strong - economic stability based on the non-decrease of natural capital (the need to direct a portion of the profit from the sale of non-renewable resources to increase the value of renewable natural capital).

The Sustainable Development Goals program includes 17 global goals and 169 related tasks:

- 1) eradication of poverty;
- 2) elimination of hunger;
- 3) health and well-being;
- 4) quality education;
- 5) gender equality;
- 6) clean water and sanitation;
- 7) cheap and clean energy;
- 8) creation of decent jobs and economic growth;
- 9) industrialization, innovation, infrastructure;
- 10) reduction of inequality;
- 11) creation of sustainable cities and comfortable living conditions;
- 12) responsible consumption and production;
- 13) combating climate change;
- 14) protection of marine ecosystems;
- 15) preservation of terrestrial ecosystems;
- 16) peace, justice and effective governance;
- 17) cooperation for sustainable development.

Global experience shows that the "green economy" stimulates regional development, achieving social stability, and increasing economic potential through the creation of new jobs in the "green economy" sectors. The "green economy" mainly contributes to economic development and ensures the growth of gross domestic product, increases the country's income, provides employment, and reduces the unemployment rate in the country. At the same time, the transition to a "green economy" reduces the risk of global threats such as climate change, the loss of minerals, and the shortage of water resources. However, if we consider global development as a whole, its commonality becomes apparent, that is, we can conclude that if all countries of the world do not choose an environmentally oriented model of economic development at a time when modern world civilization is gaining strength and reaching the peak of its power, then in the context of globalization there is a risk of the gradual decline and complete extinction of the entire planet.

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